

Social science data archive of North Macedonia

CESSDA Widening meeting
5-6 November, Skopje
assoc. prof. dr. Aneta Cekikj

Pre establishment phase (proto activities)

SEEDS project (2015-2017), Swiss national science foundation, Lead: FORS Switzerland

RRPP Data Rescue Project (2016), Swiss national science foundation

SEEDS project **deliverables**:

- Report on current conditions and practices (including survey of researchers);
- Establishment plan;
- Policy and procedures document;
- Report on integration of technical systems;
- Web site prototype;
- Local conference;
- 4 trained data specialist;
- Around 20 archived data sets (stored at FORS, University of Lausanne).

Collaboration with CESSDA ERIC

CESSDA SAW project

- Country report on current developments
- National development plan

CESSDA Widening meetings

- Lisbon, 3-4 May, 2017
- Milan, 5-6 June, 2018
- Belgrade, 14-15 November, 2018

Benefits of CESSDA ERIC membership for the scientific community in North Macedonia

- Access to CESSDA data catalogue (**21 000 studies** in English language and **9000** in other languages from across Europe);
- Participation in CESSDA training activities and training resources;
- Monitoring and implementation of international standards;
- Participation in international projects.

Collaboration with CESSDA ERIC

Current activities:

- CESSDA Mentorship Programme (Mentoring institution: Swedish National Data Service)
- SEED training *Legal and ethical issues in data management and open science*

Current developments

- MK DASS- an organizational unit of ISPJR, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje (new statute October, 2019);
- Faculty of computer science and engineering will support the IT aspects of MK DASS;
- MK DASS was appointed national service provider by the Ministry of education and science (April 2019);
- Member of CESSDA ERIC (June 2019);
- Contract with the Ministry of education and science for effective start of activities (including budget)

Key activities of MK DASS

- Preservation and dissemination of quantitative and qualitative data;
- Provision of access and support for both users and data providers;
- Permanent monitoring of compliance with the international standards in the field of data management and preservation;
- Collaboration with the wider scientific community in the field of collecting and distributing data;
- Open Access Initiative promotion.

Future activities (2020-2021)

- Creation of legal documents needed for every day working activities;
- Technical infrastructure installation;
- Promotional activities at universities' research centres and other research institutions;
- Archiving of research studies;
- Training of researchers for Data management.

Team/resources

ISPJR

- Assoc. prof. Aneta Cekikj
- Dr. Klime Babunski
- Asst. prof. Vesna Zabijakin- Chatleska
- Assoc. prof. Eleonora Serafimovska

FCSE

- Assoc. prof. Boro Jakjimovski
- Asst. Prof. Milosh Jovanovikj

WP1: Report

Institute for sociological, political and juridical research
Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje

Survey on production, preservation and use of research data among researchers

1. Methodology

- Data set of 1159 researchers from public, private and NGO sector- total population of researchers
- 181 participants completed the survey
- 15% response rate

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2. Survey participants

With what type of institution are you currently principally affiliated?

- Higher education institution
- University research institute
- Public research institute
- NGO/Think tank
- Currently not employed
- Other

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Funding sources of last research

3. Production of data

How many datasets have you produced or helped produce in the last 5 years?

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4. Archiving practices and preferences

Where is the data from your last project kept?

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ACCESS TO DATA

Q18. If you knew that your data would be preserved for the long-term in a secure environment, and shared only with accredited researchers, would you be willing to provide your data to a social science data archive?

Perceived benefits from data archive

*Q27: Would your scientific work benefit if you had better access to research data produced in Macedonia? and
Q28: Would your scientific work benefit if you had better access to international research data?*

Perceived benefits from data archive

Q35: In your view, how useful could be an institution that specializes in data archiving in your country?

N=181

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RRPP data rescue project

- 72 regional projects financed by the Regional Research Promotion Programme for the Western Balkans (RRPP) 2006-2016
- Stored at Swiss centre for the expertise in the social sciences, FORS, University of Lausanne
- <https://seedsdata.unil.ch/>

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Project and data catalogue

Free text search:

Has archived data:

[Advanced search](#)

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Show entries

Ref study	Study title	End date	Data
2	Društveni i kulturni kapital u Srbiji	30.06.2012	Yes
3	Profesija na raskršću - novinarstvo na pragu informacionog društva	30.06.2012	No
4	Predstave o obrazovnim promenama u Srbiji: refleksije o prošlosti, vizije budućnosti	31.12.2012	Yes
5	Улогата на Европската унија во демократската консолидација и менаџирањето на етничкиот конфликт во Република Македонија	28.02.2011	Yes
6	Федерализација или унитарна држава: вечна дилема на мултиетничките општества. Случајот на Република Македонија	01.02.2012	Yes
7	Mapping the Leaders in Macedonia and Albania: Can Elites Promote Positive Social Change?	28.02.2011	Yes
8	Migration and Development in Albania and Macedonia: The Effects of Remittances on Education and Health of Family Members Left Behind	31.08.2013	Yes
9	To Consume or to Self-Employ?: Evidence from Remittances' Use in Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Kosovo, with Emphasis on Crisis, Gender and Ethnicity Role	31.07.2013	Yes

Useful Resources

- Quickguides to:
- [FORbase: overview](#)
 - [Explore the catalogue](#)
 - [Get data](#)
 - [Register your study](#)
 - [Deposit your data](#)

[FAQs](#)
[Other resources](#)
[Need help?](#)

[Browse data on Nesstar](#)